

Location

Werdau (Saxony, Germany)
Berlin-Pankow (Berlin, Germany)

Innovation

Building Inspection & Valuation +
(tool) Predictive Life-Cycle
Information

Partners

TU Berlin

SUMMARY OF SCOPE AND GOALS

This work investigates the application of non-destructive testing (NDT) methods for the condition assessment and serviceability evaluation of timber roof structures. It focuses on identifying degradation mechanisms, particularly moisture-related damage, and assessing their impact through in-situ measurements. Two real-world case studies combine manual inspection techniques with continuous sensor-based monitoring to capture environmental conditions and material responses over time. The collected data supports the interpretation of damage patterns and improves the reliability of structural condition assessment.

The objective is to demonstrate how NDT-based approaches provide a data-driven basis for lifecycle assessment and support improved maintenance and life extension strategies.

DATA TYPES, TOOLS, REPOSITORIES, URLS

Data types

Timber moisture content,
temperature, relative humidity,
in-situ inspection data

Tools

Moisture sensors
Environmental sensors
Manual inspection tools
Cloud-based monitoring platform

Repository/Platform

Sensor cloud platform for data
collection and visualization

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

- › Continuous moisture monitoring in timber elements
- › Detection of moisture-related degradation risk
- › Temporal tracking of structural condition changes

IMPACT

MEDIUM

Techno-Economic
Impact

MEDIUM

Societal Impact

HIGH

Scientific Impact

IMAGES

Figure 1. Positioned moisture measurement sensor at the support point in Pankow

Figure 2. Structural Health Monitoring Platform from sensor provider

CONTACTS

Name

Benjamí Moreno Torres

Organisation

TU Berlin

Email

benjami.moreno.torres@tu-berlin.de